

Reactivity of Conjugated Systems. Part I. Condensation of Arylidene Ketones with Cyanoacetamide.

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The hypothesis that in a conjugated system of the type $R-CH=CH-CR'=O$, the ethylenic linkage is more reactive than the carbonyl with regard to substances having a reactive methylene group was investigated by Sen and collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347; Sen and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 51), who confined their attention mainly to the condensation of hydroxy-methylene ketones and β -diketones with cyanoacetamide. (cf. also Burdhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2223). But these constitute conjugated systems that are of a dynamic nature, whereas the case of permanently unsaturated ketones like benzylideneacetone, really belong to a conjugated system of a static nature, and is fundamentally different from the previous type, and hence it would not be unreasonable to suppose that the static conjugated phase included in the second type may behave differently with regard to active methylene groups. With a view to study such reactions, as well as to examine the influence, if any, of the amido-group of cyanoacetamide towards such reactions, the present work was undertaken, the results whereof have been found to throw considerable light on the mechanism of such reactions.

Sen (*loc. cit.*) has only casually mentioned the condensation between benzalacetone and cyanoacetamide, and later similar condensations have been carried out with benzalacetophenone by Kohler and his collaborators (Kohler and Souther, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2908; Kohler, Graustein and Merrill, *ibid.*, p. 2536) who describe the primary additive compound, obtained in the presence of a trace of sodium ethoxide, as an open-chain amide of the type (I), which suffered loss of a molecule of water and consequent ring closure by the action of dry hydrogen chloride or bromide in an indifferent medium.

In the course of the present work, cyanoacetamide has been condensed with (1) benzalacetophenone, (2) benzal-*p*-methylacetophenone, (3) benzalacetone and (4) α -benzalmethylethylketone both in presence of piperidine or diethylamine (Knoevenagel) and in presence of an equivalent of sodium ethoxide (Michael). It has been found that with Knoevenagel's reagent a product identical with Kohler's primary addition product (I) is obtained, while by Michael's reaction the product becomes identical with Kohler's compound (II); further, the former can be converted into the latter, by the action of gaseous hydrogen chloride (Kohler) or by heating in a sealed tube with an excess of acetic anhydride for 4 to 6 hours at 125° to 150°.

These facts, combined with the results obtained by Kohler and his school, strengthen Sen's view that Knoevenagel's reaction is merely a special case of Michael's universal reaction, and that identical products are obtained at least in the series studied herein whether Michael's or Knoevenagel's reagents are employed.

It has also been observed that the compound obtained by the action of piperidine or diethylamine, is not an open-chain amide, but is a closed-ring piperidine derivative of the type (III), while that obtained with an equivalent quantity of sodium ethoxide belongs to type (IV), and that (III) is converted into (IV) according to the following scheme:—

The constitution of (III) has been established on the following grounds:—

(a) These compounds do not give out ammonia even when warmed with dilute alkalis; on boiling, however, with aqueous alkali the liberation of ammonia becomes perceptible, due to either the rupture of the ring (*vide infra*) or to the hydrolysis of the cyano-group.

(b) When treated with sodium ethoxide in boiling alcoholic solution, they do not yield ammonia but sodium salts identical with those obtained by Michael's reaction. Reference will be made to this later.

(c) They do not yield semicarbazones or oximes, showing the absence of a free ketonic group.

(d) Further, the possibility of the existence of a compound of the type (III) is also suggested by the formation of two different iso-

mers, by the employment of piperidine and ammonia respectively. The latter compounds though not yet closely examined, easily yield ammonia on treatment with alkalis, and are hence suspected to belong to type (I).

On these considerations these compounds (Knoevenagel) have here been described as closed-ring piperidine derivatives; the aldol phase, however, readily eliminates water and as such the isolation of an acyl derivative is naturally not possible. This is strictly in conformity to the expected behaviour of such aldol ring-systems.

A word about the constitution of the tetrahydropyridine derivatives (IV) would not be out of place here. Of the three possible constitutions, (II), (IV) and (V),

Kohler and Souther (*loc. cit.*) prefer the structure (II) on account of (a) the alleged insolubility of the compound in the strongest alkalis and (b) its behaviour towards bromine.

They suggest that a compound of the type (IV) would behave like a saturated ketone towards bromine, which however need not necessarily be true, as bromine is known to be readily taken up by an unsaturated bond between carbon and nitrogen (*cf.* Curtius and Quedenfeldt, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2347; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, 58, 365; Chattaway and Walker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 979; Hantzsch, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 2773; James and Judd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1427). On the other hand they declare compounds of the type (II) to behave like a "completely enolised ketone", and hence respond to Kurt Meyer's method of bromine titration, but it seems to have escaped their notice that these compounds do not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride—a reaction that characterises all enolised ketones—and so the compounds need not possess any enolised phase under ordinary circumstances. It therefore becomes justifiable to conclude that the bromine absorption has nothing to do with the enolic phase of the substances in question. Moreover, as the authors have admitted, the bromination of these compounds is a very complicated affair, as the resulting products are very unstable and readily lose hydrobromic acid resulting in the oxidation of the molecule, and it is extremely difficult to isolate the bromination products

that are primarily formed. A critical examination of the bromination of these compounds is already in progress and would be communicated shortly. Then again, the alleged insolubility of these compounds in alkalis is not general; thus the tetrahydropyridine derivative obtained from benzalacetone, dissolves in alkalis and is reprecipitated unchanged on acidulation. Moreover, imido-compounds like (II) very frequently possess a markedly acidic property (*cf.* Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*; also Burdhan, *loc. cit.*) and so the described insolubility of these derivatives in alkalis, instead of supporting their view, serves rather to oppose it.

It must, however, be admitted that such compounds as (IV) may readily tautomerise into compounds of the type (II) and may therefore react in either phase; but this is not the same thing as saying that (IV) is (II). In view of these considerations, as well as the incapability of these compounds to yield *N*-methyl derivatives on methylation, constitution (IV) seems to be more probable, and has been admitted throughout the course of the present work.

Quite a curious result was, however, obtained when attempting to hydrolyse the cyano-group either in compound (III) or (IV). When heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid in sealed tubes, the ring of these compounds was completely ruptured, resulting in the formation of nitrogen-free open-chain derivatives. When these primary condensation products were treated with concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of methyl or ethyl alcohols at ordinary temperature, esters of open-chain dibasic acids were obtained. The acids themselves could be obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of these esters, which lost carbon dioxide on melting and yielded compounds identical with those obtained by hydrolysing them with concentrated hydrochloric acid. These monobasic acids crystallise well and correspond to formula (VIII) on analysis, but their properties could not be reconciled to that structure on account of their insolubility in sodium bicarbonate solution even on long keeping, whilst they went into complete solution quite readily in caustic alkalis, and slowly in carbonated alkalis, like lactones; acidulation of the alkaline solutions always gave the original substances back. The presence of a ketonic group was proved by their yielding well-defined oximes and semicarbazones in the usual way. Indirect titration with alkali showed that they behave like monobasic acids.

It is therefore concluded that these compounds undergo the so-called keto-lactol tautomerism, (*cf.* Qudrat-i-Khuda, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

1929, 201) and normally exist in the forms (IX) and (X) respectively which in the presence of substances that tend to anchor either the ketonic or the carboxylic group, assume the forms (VII) and (VIII) and react as di- and mono-basic ketonic acids respectively. It is thus that the formation of semicarbazones and oximes as well as their neutralisation by alkalis is explained.

That these compounds possess a lactol modification is further proved by the formation of an unsaturated lactone (XI) when acted upon by acetyl chloride or acetic anhydride (*cf.* Vorländer and Knotzsch, *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 333). These unsaturated lactones do not yield semicarbazones or oximes, and are reconverted into the original lactols on warming with aqueous alkalis.

This whole change is represented by the following scheme: -

The identities of these compounds were further established by synthesising them from the condensation products between the corresponding arylidene ketones and malonic ester in the presence of sodium ethoxide according to the method of Vorländer and his collaborators (*loc. cit.*) when, excepting in the cases of benzalacetone and

α -benzalmethylethylketone (*i.e.*, when R in Ph·CH=CH-CO-R contains a primary carbon atom), identical lactols and lactol acids were obtained. When R contains a primary carbon atom, a dihydro-resorcinol derivative is obtained, thus:—

The products do not yield semicarbazones, give colouration with ferric chloride and possess all the properties ascribed to them by Vorländer.

It would thus appear that even in a static conjugated double-bonded system, the addition of the methylene group of cyanoacetamide takes place at the ethylenic linkage and that the amido-group is only helpful in closing the rings through the carbonyl of the conjugated system. The amido-group has no directive influence of its own; acetamide could not be condensed with any of these ketones under the experimental conditions mentioned herein.

The rupture of the pyridine ring appears to be rather improbable but this is due to the extreme instability of partially reduced pyridine rings. To quote Meyer and Jacobson, ("Lehrbuch der Organischen Chemie, 1923, Vol. II, Part III, p. 812). "Interessant sind diese Stoffe (tetrahydro-pyridine) besonders durch die Beziehungen, welche sie mit acyclischen, durch Wasser-aufnahme und Ringspaltung aus ihnen gebildeten δ -Amino-ketonen verknüpfen, z. B.:

These tetrahydropyridine derivatives contain two hydrogen atoms that are easily removable by bromine (*vide supra*) and by nitrous acid. These dehydrogenated compounds are found to be identical with the condensation products of the corresponding β -diketones and cyanoacetamide (*cf.* Issoglio, *Atti. R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 1905, **40**, 495; also Basu, *private communication*). Consequently these H-atoms come from the 4th and 5th carbon atoms of the ring. Such a conclusion has found support in the fact (to be described later) that when the hydrogen atom in position 4 is substituted, it is not dehydrogenated either by bromine or by nitrous acid. These compounds are readily hydrolysed by means of 75% sulphuric acid or concentrated hydrochloric acid into known hydroxy-pyridine derivatives, thus:—

Further, in the presence of alcoholic ammonia these tetrahydropyridine derivatives undergo reciprocal oxidation and reduction in the following way:—

Such a phenomenon has been known from early times (*cf.* Hantzsch, *Annalen*, 1882, **215**, 370; Paul and Strasser, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2756; Griess and Harrow, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 2743; Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 1790; Knoevenagel and others, *ibid.*, 1903, **36**, 2813). The results of the present investigation in this line will be shortly communicated.

Kohler and his collaborators have, in their work, noticed many of these points, but their statements lack in conclusive evidence in support of their views and besides, some unfortunate inaccuracies in their work, compelled the present worker to repeat a good many of their experiments before any satisfactory conclusion could be drawn from their statements.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method.—The primary condensation and the following conversions were carried out under similar conditions in all the cases cited below, and the general procedure is given here in detail. The yields and other characteristic properties have been given under the respective headings. The cyanoacetamide employed was prepared by the method of Thole and Thorpe, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 422) crystallised from alcohol and dried in vacuum, m.p. 118-20°.

(1) *Michael's Method.*—One atom of sodium was dissolved in a conical flask in just sufficient absolute ethyl alcohol, such that no sodium ethoxide separated on cooling; to this, one molecule of cyanoacetamide similarly dissolved in boiling absolute alcohol was added, when the sodium salt separated out. One molecule of the ketone, dissolved in a little absolute alcohol was then added to this mixture, at about 50°, the flask corked up and the mixture shaken vigorously till the sodium compound went into complete solution; the mixture became warmer and the colour deepened from pale to deep brownish-yellow. In some cases the sodium salt of the reaction product separated in the course of a few hours, while in some, it did so after a day's time. After two days, water was added to the mixture, till the solid went into solution, and the free condensation product was obtained by acidulation with dilute hydrochloric acid. A purer product could be obtained by saturating the alcoholic suspension of the reaction mixture with carbon dioxide when the free condensation product, along with sodium bicarbonate, separated out. The tetrahydropyridine derivative so obtained, was filtered, washed with hot water till free from acids and sodium salts, dried in *vacuo*, and crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid. (The employment of an equivalent quantity of sodium ethoxide did not in any case yield any appreciable quantity of the trimolecular compound described by Kohler).

(2) *Knoevenagel's Method.*—One molecule of cyanoacetamide was dissolved with warming in so much water that it did not separate on cooling, one molecule of the ketone was similarly dissolved in alcohol, the two were mixed in a conical flask, and the mixture made clear by the addition of more alcohol; a little piperidine or diethylamine (usually 1 c. c. for every 4.2 g. of cyanoacetamide) was then added to the mixture, the flask loosely corked and left over, preferably at about 40-50° (an asbestos board on the top of a steam-oven answers the purpose well), when usually the condensation product began to separate in the course of a day or two and became fully separated in one or two weeks. The product was collected, washed with a little rectified spirit and the mother-liquor left over again after the addition of a little more of the amine, when some more condensation product separated in about another week which was again collected in the usual way. Acidulation of the mother-liquor gave some more impure product, unprofitable to recover. The substance was obtained in a sufficiently pure state and could be further purified by crystallisation from alcohol or acetone. This was the hydroxypiperidone derivative (III).

The above compound when dehydrated by a suitable reagent, was nearly quantitatively transformed into the Michael's product. For this purpose the following methods have been employed with success:—

(a) By heating the Knoevenagel's condensation product in a sealed tube with an excess of acetic anhydride at 125° to 150° for 4 to 6 hours. The resulting solution was then evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the residue extracted and crystallised from alcohol.

(b) On saturating a chloroform or carbon tetrachloride suspension of the compound with dry hydrogen chloride gas in the cold; the solid first went into solution and then reappeared, as a paste, owing to the separation of water. It was next left to attain the room temperature and then treated with cold water, and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The chloroform or carbon tetrachloride was then removed, the solid collected and purified.

(3) *Hydrolysis of the Condensation Product.*—No general method could be made to answer all the cases under review. The following methods have, however, been employed according to their applicability. As has been referred to already, both Knoevenagel's as well as Michael's condensation products are hydrolysed into the

lactol compounds when subjected to hydrolysis by either of the following ways:—

(a) Heating in a sealed tube with 5 to 10% sulphuric acid or with 33% hydrochloric acid converted them directly into the lactol (X) which could be isolated by diluting the solution and separating the so obtained solid; this could then be purified by dissolving in dilute sodium carbonate, filtering and reprecipitating by mineral acids.

(b) Dissolving the condensation products in the minimum quantity of cold concentrated sulphuric acid, leaving overnight in a well closed flask (when probably the CN group is converted into the CO·NH₂ group) and then poured into well cooled methyl or ethyl alcohol, and left again at room temperature for 8 to 10 hours, after which it was treated with cracked ice when the methyl or ethyl ester of the dibasic acid (VII) separated. This when warmed with an excess of 5% aqueous potash, on the water-bath till the whole went into solution, cooled, filtered and acidulated with mineral acids, gave the lactol acid (IX) which could be further purified as above.

These lactol acids lost carbon dioxide on melting, and when kept in a molten state for a few minutes, till the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased, and then cooled, they solidified into beautifully crystalline bodies, identical with the lactols mentioned above.

(4) *Dehydrogenation of the Michael's Condensation Products.*—This could be effected by various ways, of which only the nitrous acid method has been given here in detail. The action of alcoholic ammonia, bromine and hydrogen peroxide would form the subject matter of a future communication.

One molecule of the Michael's condensation product was dissolved in a slight excess of glacial acetic acid and cooled in ice, a little more than two molecules of sodium nitrite dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and well cooled, was then added little by little to the previous solution with good shaking, such that there was no appreciable liberation of NO₂; when all the nitrite solution was added, the flask was left for an hour in the cold, and then allowed to attain the the room temperature and left for about a week. The oxidation product which generally separated out, was then filtered, washed with cold alcohol and crystallised.

(5) *Hydrolysis of the Cyanopyridone Derivatives.*—This could be effected by heating the cyanopyridones either in a sealed tube

with fuming hydrochloric acid at 125—50° for 3 to 4 hours, or by boiling with 75 to 80% sulphuric acid under reflux for 5 to 10 minutes till CO₂ ceased to evolve. The hydrochloric acid hydrolysis product could be isolated by evaporating to dryness on a water-bath, washing the residue with water and crystallising from alcohol. From the sulphuric acid reaction mixture, the product usually separated on dilution, which was filtered, washed free from acid and crystallised from alcohol.

(6) *Condensation of Malonic Ester with Unsaturated Ketones and their Hydrolysis.*—The condensation was carried out exactly as described by Vorländer (*loc. cit.*). The mixture was left over for a day at room temperature, diluted with water, the aqueous solution washed with ether to remove any unchanged ketone or ester, and acidulated by dilute hydrochloric acid when the condensation product usually separated as a paste which solidified on cooling and scratching. This was then hydrolysed with excess of 5% aqueous potash in the usual way, when the corresponding lactol acid (IX) or the dihydroresorcinol derivative was obtained. The lactol acid could be converted into the corresponding lactol by heating. When this lactol was dehydrated with acetyl chloride or acetic anhydride, it was converted into the unsaturated lactone (XI). On treatment with aqueous potash and subsequent acidulation of the solution the original lactol was regenerated.

The dihydroresorcinol derivatives obtained from benzalacetone or α -benzalmethylethylketone, on boiling under reflux with an excess of barium hydroxide solution, containing 2½ times their weight of Ba(OH)₂ were converted into the lactol acid (IX) which on melting, formed the lactol (X) identical with those obtained from the corresponding cyanoacetamide condensation products.

I. *Condensation of Benzalacetophenone with Cyanoacetamide.*

Benzalacetophenone was prepared by the method of Kohler and Chadwell ("Organic synthesis" II, 1). Yield 90% ; m.p. 55-6°.

(1) *By Michael's method:—Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine.*—The sodium salt of the condensation product began to separate within a couple of hours, and was completely separated in a day or two, and separation of the condensation product by mineral acids gave a fairly pure product, yield being about 87%. It was fairly soluble in the alcohols, pyridine

and acetic acid, sparingly so in ether and benzene, and almost insoluble in chloroform and petroleum ether. It was insoluble in dilute acids or alkalis, soluble in strong sulphuric acid, gave no coloration with ferric chloride. It crystallised from acetic acid or alcohol in small prisms; m. p. 220-22°. (Found: C, 78.85; H, 5.28; N, 10.43. $C_{18}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 78.83; H, 5.11; N, 10.22 per cent.).

(2) *By Knoevenagel's method:—Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-6-hydrozypiperidine.*—The mixture began to deposit the condensation product in a day, and about 75% of the theoretical quantity could be obtained after a week. It was fairly soluble in the alcohols, acetone and acetic acid, sparingly so in ether, benzene and chloroform and insoluble in petroleum ether; insoluble in dilute alkalis and acids, soluble in strong sulphuric acid; gave no coloration with ferric chloride. It crystallised from methyl alcohol or acetone in colourless prismatic needles, m. p. 161-62°. (Found: C, 73.61; H, 5.56; N, 9.33. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.97; H, 5.48; N, 9.59 per cent.).

This compound on treatment with dry hydrogen chloride in chloroform suspension or on heating with an excess of acetic anhydride in a sealed tube at 120-25° for 6 hours was converted into the Michael's compound, identified with a specimen from stock.

(3) *Hydrolysis of the condensation products:—Formation of dimethyl ester of α -carboxy- β -phenyl- γ -benzoylbutyric acid, and the corresponding lactol acid and lactol.*—

(a) The methyl ester crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol as white prismatic needles, m. p. 108°, very soluble in all common organic solvents. (Found: C, 70.41; H, 6.06. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88 per cent.).

(b) The lactol acid was obtained in an yield of 60% by hydrolysing the above ester. It was very soluble in all organic solvents excepting petroleum ether and benzene. Crystallised from benzene with a few drops of methyl alcohol, it came in fine short white needles, m. p. 152.4° with decomposition; it dissolved freely in alkalis, carbonates and bicarbonates from which it was precipitated unchanged on acidulation. (Found: C, 68.97; H, 5.33. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.23; H, 5.13 per cent.). 0.2050 G. of the substance required 12.9 c.c. of *N*/10-alkali for neutralisation showing it to be a dibasic acid.

(c) The lactol was obtained in a nearly theoretical yield when the above compound was kept in a molten state till effervescence

ceased. On cooling, the pale yellow melt solidified in long needles; it was fairly soluble in all common solvents, and crystallised from methyl alcohol in beautiful colourless needles, m. p. 158°. It dissolved readily in caustic alkalis, slowly, in carbonates and was insoluble in bicarbonate solution. This compound could be directly obtained when either of the original condensation products were heated with about 10 times their weight of strong hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube for 6 hours at 125° and treated as usual. (Found: C, 75.84; H, 6.19. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.12; H, 5.94 per cent.). 0.1208 G. of the substance required 4.4 c.c. of *N*/10-alkali, corresponding to a monobasic acid. The semicarbazone, obtained as usual melted with decomposition at 215°.

(4) *Formation of 3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone*.—The compound separated completely during the course of about a week when it was filtered off, washed with alcohol, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, or a mixture of equal volumes of pyridine and alcohol (charcoal) as pale yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 320° (Kohler gives it to be 313-15°). It was found to be identical with a specimen obtained by the condensation of cyanoacetamide with dibenzoyl methane (Basu, *private communication*). Was very sparingly soluble in all common organic solvents, excepting glacial acetic acid and pyridine. It dissolved in alkalis, and in strong sulphuric acid; gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: N, 10.12. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 10.30 per cent.).

(5) *Hydrolysis of the Cyanopyridone:—Formation of 2-hydroxy-4:6-diphenylpyridine*.—The hydrolysis could be best effected by taking the cyanopyridone (1 g.) in 75 per cent. sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) in which it dissolved giving a yellow solution, and boiling it for about 5 to 10 minutes, till the evolution of CO_2 ceased. On cooling and diluting, the hydroxypyridine separated as a yellow solid which crystallised from rectified spirit as pale yellow needles, m.p. 208° (Kohler gives 210°). This was identified with a sample obtained by the hydrolysis of the condensation product between dibenzoylmethane and cyanoacetamide. It was very soluble in all common organic solvents, excepting petroleum ether. It dissolved in alkalis from which it was reprecipitated unchanged on acidulation and gave a brownish red coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 5.79. $C_{17}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 5.66 per cent.).

(6) *Condensation with malonic ester:—Formation of diethyl ester of α -carboxy- β -phenyl- γ -benzoylbutyric acid*. The ester was

obtained in the usual way. Yield was equal to the weight of the ketone employed; crystallised from methyl or ethyl alcohol it was obtained as colourless needles, melting at 150°. (Found: C, 72.01; H, 6.88. $C_{22}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 71.74; H, 6.52 per cent.). On hydrolysis with aqueous KOH, the lactol acid m.p. 152-4° was obtained (Vorländer and Knotzsch, m.p. 144°). This was converted into the corresponding lactol by heating; m.p. 158° (Vorländer and Knotzsch, m.p. 155-56°; oxime, m.p. 144-46°). These were found to be identical with the corresponding compounds obtained from the tetrahydropyridine derivatives. The unsaturated lactone obtained by dehydration as usual, crystallised from ether or petroleum ether, m.p. 58°; on heating with aqueous alkalis it regenerated the original lactol.

II. Condensation of Benzal-p-methylacetophenone with Cyanoacetamide.

Benzal-p-methylacetophenone was prepared in the same way as benzalacetophenone, only about twice the volume of alcohol had to be employed and the mixture had to be left for about a week, before the unsaturated ketone could be obtained in a solid state. Yield about 80 per cent. After crystallisation from alcohol it was obtained in lemon-yellow crystals melting at 75°

(1) *By Michael's method*:—Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine.—It was obtained by hydrochloric acid separation in an yield of about 90 per cent. of theory. Crystallised from alcohol it was obtained in light white clusters of soft needles, m.p. 185°; excepting for its better solubility it resembled its lower homologue in all other properties. (Found: N, 9.78. $C_{19}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 9.78 per cent.).

(2) *By Knoevenagel's method*:—Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-p-tolyl-6-hydroxypiperidine.—The condensation product separated during the course of three or four days, yield 75 per cent. crystallised from dilute acetone it came as a light white powder, m.p. 230°. (Found: N, 8.98. $C_{19}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.15 per cent.). This compound could be quantitatively transformed into the tetrahydropyridine derivative as in the previous case.

(3) *Hydrolysis of the condensation products*.—These changes could be effected in an exactly similar way as in the previous case.

(a) *Dimethyl ester of α -carboxy- β -phenyl- γ -p-tolyl butyric acid* resembled the corresponding γ -benzoyl derivative in all properties but was more soluble than it. Crystallised from methyl alcohol it

melted at 95°. (Found: C, 70·87; H, 5·98. $C_{21}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 71·18; H, 6·21 per cent.)

(b) The lactol acid obtained and crystallised as before melted at 150° with decomposition. (Found: C, 70·21; H, 5·79. $C_{10}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69·94; H, 5·52 per cent.). 0·1096 G. of the acid required 6·4 c.c. of *N*/10-alkali, indicating it to be dibasic.

(c) The lactol obtained either by heating the above compound or by direct hydrolysis of the original condensation products by concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube was obtained as fine colourless needles that melted at 175°. (Found: C, 76·07; H, 6·63. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 76·80; H, 6·88 per cent.). 0·0536 G. of the substance required 1·9 c.c. of *N*/10-alkali, corresponding to a monobasic acid of the same formula. The semicarbazone obtained as usual, melted at 222°, with decomposition.

(4) *Formation of 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone.*—The compound was obtained similarly as in the previous case, yield about 60-70 per cent. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) it was obtained in pale yellow needles, m.p. 269°. (Found: N, 9·78. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9·78 per cent.)

(5) *Formation of 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl-6-p-tolylpyridine.*—The above on hydrolysis with 80 per cent. sulphuric acid gave the hydroxypyridine in an yield of about 90 per cent. Crystallised from rectified spirit (charcoal) it came as light yellow needles, m.p. 226-28°; it was soluble in alkalis, gave a brownish red coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 5·46. $C_{18}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 5·36 per cent.)

(6) *Condensation with malonic ester.*—(a) The diethyl ester obtained as before crystallised from methyl alcohol and resembled the lower homologue in all its properties, m.p. 123°. (Found: C, 71·98; H, 6·63. $C_{20}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 72·25; H, 6·81 per cent.)

(b) The lactol acid crystallised from benzene containing a little methyl alcohol melted at 150° with decomposition forming the lactol.

(c) The lactol when crystallised from rectified spirit melted at 175°; both these compounds were identified with the corresponding compounds obtained from the cyanoacetamide condensation products.

(d) The unsaturated lactone was obtained by the action of acetic anhydride as usual. Crystallised from ether in long needles it melted at 98°; on boiling with aqueous alkali it was reconverted into the original lactol.

III. *Condensation of Benzalacetone with Cyanoacetamide.*

The ketone was obtained from the market. It was not found necessary to recrystallise it and so it was used as obtained.

(1) *Michael's reaction*:—*Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine.*—The sodium salt of the condensation product separated more slowly, in this case, the completion of the reaction requiring about 3 to 4 days. The condensation product was separated by carbon dioxide, filtered, washed with a little alcohol and finally, with hot water. The alcoholic solution gave a further quantity on concentration, the total yield being about 65 per cent. It dissolved in alkalis, from which it was obtained unchanged on acidulation; was very soluble in pyridine and acetic acid, less so in the alcohols, acetone and benzene, and insoluble in petroleum ether and water. It crystallised from hot amyl or ethyl alcohol in fine colourless prisms, melting at 267° and darkening a few degrees earlier. (Found: N, 13.59. $C_{13}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 13.20 per cent.).

(2) *Knoevenagel's method*:—*Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-6-hydroxypiperidins.*—The reaction took about a fortnight to 3 weeks for completion; total yield about 60 per cent. Moderately soluble in the alcohols, acetone and water, more so in acetic acid and pyridine, insoluble in benzene and petroleum ether. Soluble in dilute alkalis and acids by virtue of its solubility in water. It crystallised from alcohol or water in colourless needles melting with decomposition at 195-96°. (Found: N, 12.93. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.17 per cent.). For conversion into the tetrahydropyridine derivative it required a little longer keeping with gaseous hydrochloric acid in carbon tetrachloride suspension (half to one hour at room temperature) as well as longer heating (8 to 10 hours at 125-30°) with acetic anhydride than in the previous cases. The products of both treatment were identical with the Michael compound.

(3) *Hydrolysis of the condensation products.* The lactol was directly obtained by heating either of the condensation products with an excess of 5 per cent. sulphuric acid in a sealed tube at 125-30° for 6 to 8 hours when it separated as a heavy oil, which solidified on ice-cooling and scratching. It was purified as usual and crystallised from a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene in white granular crystals, m.p. 85°. (Found: C, 69.72; H, 7.07. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires

C, 69.9; H, 6.6 per cent.) 0.1864 G. of the substance required 6.6 c.c. of *N*/10-alkali corresponding to a monobasic acid of the same composition. Its semicarbazone, obtained in the usual way, melted at 170° with decomposition. On treatment with acetic anhydride it gave an oily product, which regenerated the original lactol on heating with aqueous alkalis.

(4) *Formation of 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone.*—The dehydrogenation product did not separate even on considerable dilution of the reaction mixture. It separated as a light brown powder on neutralising the acetic acid by sodium carbonate. It crystallised from acetic acid in fine needles that melted at 275°-76°. Identified with a sample of 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone prepared by Basu (*private communication*). It was soluble in most organic solvents and also somewhat in water; it dissolved in dilute alkalis quite readily, but did not give any colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 13.53. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.38 per cent.).

(5) The above could be readily hydrolysed into 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl-6-methylpyridine by either of the hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid methods. It crystallised from alcohol in fine needles, melting at 206.7° and possessed all the properties ascribed to it by the previous authors.

(6) Condensation with malonic ester, gave the dihydroresorcinol derivative described by Vorländer (*loc. cit.*). This was converted into the corresponding lactol (described by Vorländer as β -phenyl- γ -acetylbutyric acid m.p. 84°; oxime, m.p. 127°) by boiling with barium hydroxide, followed by subsequent heating; crystallised from a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene, it melted at 85° and was identified with the specimen obtained from the corresponding cyanoacetamide condensation product.

IV. Condensation of α -Benzal-methylethylketone with Cyanoacetamide.

The ketone was prepared by the method of Harries and Müller, (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 968, 971) supplemented by the modification of Drake and Allen, jr. ("Organic Synthesis" II, 17); b.p. 225-30°/15 mm. Yield 60 per cent.

(1) *By Michael's reaction:*—*Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-ethyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine.*—The sodium salt of

the condensation product did not separate as happened in the other cases; separation of the free condensation product was best effected by CO_2 , yield about 60 per cent. It was fairly soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and pyridine, sparingly so in benzene and acetone and insoluble in petroleum ether and water. Crystallised from rectified spirit, it melted at $178-80^\circ$; and resembled its lower homologue in other properties. (Found: N, 12.12. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 12.39 per cent.).

(2) *By Knoevenagel's reaction*:—*Formation of 2-iso-3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-ethyl-6-hydroxy-piperidine*.—Obtained as usual, the yield barely reaching about 45 per cent. sparingly soluble in alcohol and benzene, moderately so in acetone, insoluble in petroleum ether and water and very soluble in acetic acid. Crystallised from dilute acetone it melted with decomposition at $235-36^\circ$. (Found: N, 11.83. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 11.48 per cent.). It could be converted into the Michael compound in the usual way.

(3) *Hydrolysis of the condensation products*.—The lactol was directly obtained by hydrolysing either of the condensation products by heating in a sealed tube with 10 per cent. sulphuric acid at $140-150^\circ$ for 6 hours. It was very soluble in most solvents, crystallised from benzene, it melted at 108° , and resembled the other members of the series. (Found: C, 70.67; H, 7.51. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.9; H, 7.27 per cent.). 0.1038 G. of the substance neutralised 4.9 c.c. *N*/10 alkali showing it to be monobasic. The unsaturated lactone was obtained as an uncrystallisable oil, which on heating with aqueous alkalis gave the original lactol back. Semicarbazone, obtained as usual, melted at 165° with decomposition.

(4) *Dehydrogenation* by means of nitrous acid gave a product that separated only on dilution of the reaction mixture; *3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-ethyl-2-pyridone* separated from dilute acetic acid in prisms melting at 268° . (Found: N, 12.67. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}$, requires N, 12.50 per cent.).

(5) The *hydrolysis* of the above compound was effected by means of 75 per cent. sulphuric acid as usual; *2-hydroxy-4-phenyl-6-ethylpyridine* was obtained in fine needles from alcohol, melting at 165° and resembled the other members of this series in all other respects. (Found: N, 7.26. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}$ requires N, 7.04 per cent.).

(5) *Condensation with malonic ester* gave rise to a dihydro-resorcinol derivative. The dihydroresoreyl ester was obtained as

usual and crystallised from rectified spirit in large colourless prisms that gradually become yellowish on keeping, melting at 120° . (Found: C, 69.89; H, 6.85. $C_{13}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.01; H, 6.57 per cent.). The *dihydroresorcinol* was obtained in the same way as in the preceding case which crystallised from rectified spirit in small yellowish granular prisms melting at 214° . (Found: C, 76.98; H, 7.14. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 6.93 per cent.). This was converted into the corresponding *lactol* in the same way as above and identified with that obtained from the cyanoacetamide condensation product, m.p. 108° .

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